

The carbonyl stretching mode present at 1740 cm^{-1} in pure acetic anhydride is slightly lowered to about 1726 cm^{-1} in these double acetates suggesting that the solvent molecules are not coordinated to the metal; rather they are held by the cation ion-dipole interaction which is in accordance with the T. G. A. studies as the solvent molecules are lost at comparatively low temperature. Symmetric and asymmetric stretching modes of the acetate group have been employed for the structural elucidation⁵. The difference in the symmetric and asymmetric carboxy group in a compound where acetate group acts as bidentate bridging group is expected not to be grossly different from that observed for the acetate group in sodium acetate and both the stretching modes move to the higher regions⁶. As no bands are observed around $1600\text{--}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$, it rules out the possibility of bridging acetate group⁷ present in these compounds. Since the difference in the symmetric and asymmetric stretching modes is reduced and both the bands move to the lower region, it indicates that the acetate group is acting as symmetric chelating group. Apart from these bands, the bands, though low in intensity are also present at their original position and the difference in the symmetric and asymmetric stretching modes of the carboxy groups are not different from those found in $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\cdot\text{OAc}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ where acetate group acts as a monodentate ligand⁸ suggesting that in the compounds $\text{M}_2[\text{Co}(\text{OAc})_4]\cdot 4\text{Ac}_2\text{O}$ two of the acetate groups act as bidentate chelating agents and the rest of the acetate groups act as monodentate ligands and the central atom acquire a coordination number of six. A slight splitting of the asymmetric stretching mode in some of these compounds ($10\text{--}16\text{ cm}^{-1}$), is either due to the difference in the force constant or due to solid state interactions within the lattice. Metal-oxygen stretching mode expected to be in the range $400\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed at $\sim 420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the case of cobalt compounds and at $\sim 410\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the case of nickel compounds. These modes are independent of the alkali metal used and these are observed at the same position as reported in literature^{9,10}. There is no experimental evidence to show that acetic anhydride molecules are directly attached to the transition metals; they are rather surrounding the cation and held in the crystal lattice by ion-dipole interaction.

The possible formation of these double acetates may be visualised as :

A possible structure where acetate group may act as bidentate chelating as well monodentate ligand may be postulated as shown at the bottom of the left column.

References

1. B. N. GRIFFITH and J. LEWIS, "Progress in Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. VI. Interscience Publishers, Inc. New York, 1964, p. 37.
2. S. KIRSCHNER and R. KIESLINY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 4174.
3. D. DOLLIMORE and D. NICHOLSON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 739.
4. H. N. RANDALL, R. G. FOWLER, N. FUSON and J. R. DANGL, "I. r. Determination of Organic Structures", Van-Nostrand, 1949.
5. L. J. BELLAMY, "The I. R. Spectra of Complex Molecules" John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York, 1966.
6. K. NAKAMOTO, J. FUJITA, S. TANAKA and M. KOBAYASHI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4904.
7. T. A. STEPHENSON, G. M. MOREHOUSE, A. R. POWELL, J. P. HEFFER and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 3623, 1965.
8. G. A. BARCLAY and C. H. L. KENNARD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 5244, 1961.
9. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. MORIMOTO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 346.
10. K. NAKAMOTO, P. J. MCCARTHY and B. MINIATAS, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1965, **21**, 1.

Study of the Chelate of Divalent Manganese with 2-Hydroxy-1, 4-Naphthoquinone (Lawson).

K. D. JAIN, A. K. JAIN* & R. K. SHARMA.

Chemical Laboratories, D. A. V. College, Dehra Dun and Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, U. P.

Manuscript received 29 August 1974; revised 8 March 1975; accepted 4 April 1975.

SURVEY of literature reveals that 2-Hydroxy⁻¹, 4-Naphthoquinone (Lawson) has found its application in qualitative and quantitative estimations of various metals¹⁻⁴. Recently we have studied and established structures of chelates of lawson with various metals⁵. In the present communication the composition, nature of structure, stability constant and free energy of formation of Mn^{++} : Lawson chelate is reported.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Lawson (K. K. Laboratories N. C. Plains view, New York, A. R.) and manganese chloride (B. D. H. AnalaR) were prepared by dissolving the respective compounds in double distilled ethyl alcohol (absolute).

To isolate the complex, 200 ml of Lawson (alcoholic) solution (0.01M) was added slowly, to 200 ml manganese chloride (0.01M) with constant stirring. The solution was then warmed and allowed to stand overnight. The deep red coloured crystals were filtered, washed with alcohol and dried at $62^\circ\text{--}67^\circ$.

* For Correspondence

The isolated complex was analysed for metal and Chlorine contents.

Baush and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer for absorbance measurements and Parkin-Elmer infra cord spectrophotometer for Infra-red spectra were used.

Result and Discussion

Nature of chelate: Mixtures containing equal proportions of manganese chloride and lawsone were mixed and the absorbance measured⁶. The absorption maximum of the complex (wine red in colour) was found to be at 480 nm.

Composition of the chelate: The composition of the chelate was established by the method of Joh's continuous variation⁷, Molar ratio⁸ slope ratio⁹, and Dey¹⁰. A large number of observations were taken at 480 nm. and it was found that the ratio of Mn⁺ ; lawsone in the chelate is 1:1.

Evaluation of stability constant and Free energy: The stability constant calculated from the absorbance data by molar ratio method is 3.6×10^5 and free energy formation as calculated from $-\Delta F = RT \ln K$ is -7.6 K. Cals/mole.

Molecular Formula of the chelate: From analysis it was found that amount of Mn in the chelate is 12.1% and amount of Chlorine is 7.8% which correspond to the formula $[(C_{10}H_6O_8) Mn^+ (C_2H_5OH)_4] Cl^-$ calculated values are 12.3% for Mn and 7.9% for chlorine.

Structure of the chelate: The O-H band at 3125 cm^{-1} in the ligand completely disappeared in the complex indicating thereby that proton is liberated during complex formation. The lowering of C=O stretch of the ligand from 1650 cm^{-1} to 1630 cm^{-1} in the complex indicates that Co-ordination of lawsone is through carbonyl oxygen.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Director, I. I. P. Dehra Dun for providing I. R. Spectra of these compounds.

References

1. B. D. JAIN and S. P. SINGAL., *Current Sci.* India, 1962 **31**, 279.
2. A.P. ZOZULYA and V. M. PESHKOVA., *Zhur, Neorg, Khim*, 1959, **4**, 379.
3. I. H. SIFFERT and W. C. PURDY., *J. Electroanal Chem.* 1966, **11**, 302.
4. M.K. AKHMADLI, A.A. SADYKHOVA, P.B. GRANOVSKAYA, I. S. LOZOVSKAYA and S. ALIEVA., *Azerli Khim. Zh.*, 1963, **5**, 93.
5. S. S. SAWHNEY., Ph. D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1972.
6. B. S. GARG, R. P. SINGH and M. KATYAL., *Indian J. Appl. Chem.* 1971, **34**, 17.
7. S. K. BANERJI and A. K. DEY., *Z. Anal. Chem.* 1961, **30**, 179.
8. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES., *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.* 1944, **16**, 111.
9. A. F. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1950, **72**, 4488.
10. DEY, *Nature Lond.*, 1956, **158**, 95.

Studies on Indian Medicinal Plants-Part XXXIV* Triterpenes from *Grewia asiatica*

SUBHAGATA CHATTOPADHYAY and S. C. PAKRASHI*

Department of Medicinal Chemistry
Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta-700032.

Manuscript Received 6 February 1975 ; accepted 22 March 1975

THE recent report¹ on the isolation of β -sitosterol, β -amyrin and betulin from *Grewia asiatica* Linn(Syn. *G. subinaequalis* DC)^{2,3}, N. O. Tiliaceae, prompted us to publish our work on the stem-bark of the same species. We, however, encountered friedelin, betulin, lupeol and lupenone.

Experimental

All m. p. s. are uncorrected and $[\alpha]_D$ measured in CHCl_3 . Silica gel was used for column chromatography. The identity of compounds were established by direct comparison (m. p., m. m p, $[\alpha]_D$, tlc and ir) with authentic specimens. The analytical data were in good agreement with the theory.

Dried and milled stem-bark (2 kg) of *Grewia asiatica* was successively extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with light petrol, C_6H_6 and CH_2Cl_2 .

The light petrol extract on concentration separated a yellow solid (fraction A) which was filtered and the filtrate evaporated (Fraction B). The fractions were separately chromatographed.

From fraction A, light petrol - C_6H_6 (3 : 1) eluted an oil (fraction A₁) while the same solvent mixture (1 : 1) afforded lupeol (5g), m. p. 212°-214°, $[\alpha]_D^{+27}$ in colourless needles (CHCl_3 -MeOH); acetate (C_6H_6 - CHCl_3), m. p. 215°, $[\alpha]_D^{+47}$. Further elution with C_6H_6 - CH_2Cl_2 (1 : 1) yielded betulin (3 g), m. p. 254°-256°, $[\alpha]_D^{+21}$ in colourless needles (C_6H_6 -MeOH); dibenzoate, (C_6H_6 -MeOH), m. p. 178°-179°, $[\alpha]_D^{+37}$.

Elution of fraction B with light petrol- C_6H_6 (3 : 1) gave an oil (fraction B₁) followed by lupeol.

The combined oily fractions A₁ and B₁ (0.5 g) was rechromatographed. Light petrol eluted an oil (0.1 g) which crystallised (EtOH) in colourless short stout needles, m. p. 170°-171°, $[\alpha]_D^{+61.5}$, ν_{max} 1705, 1640, 890 cm^{-1} , identified as lupenone. Further elution with the same solvent yielded a solid (0.1g) crystallising (EtOH) in colourless needles, m. p. 260°, $[\alpha]_D^{-25}$; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1710 cm^{-1} identified as friedelin.

On similar chromatographic resolutions, the C_6H_6 extract yielded lupenone (0.011 g), lupeol (0.023 g) and betulin (0.01 g) while the CH_2Cl_2 extract afforded lupenone (0.012 g) and lupeol (0.05 g).

References

1. K. C. JOSHI, L. PRAKASH and R. K. SHAH., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 830.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, S.L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, p. 128.
3. B. N. SASTRI., "The Wealth of India, Raw Materials", Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, vol. IV, p. 262.

* For Part XXXIII in the Series See E. ALI V. S. GIRI and S. C. PAKRASHI *Phyto Chemistry*, (in the press).
To whom all correspondences to be addressed.